

Beyond the Paper: Evaluating Repository Coverage and Citation Impact of Heterogeneous Research Outputs at UNIBO

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Abstract

Purpose. This study evaluates the representation and dissemination of diverse research outputs - such as software, databases, exhibitions, audio-visual materials, and others - produced by researchers at the University of Bologna (UNIBO) and collected across various repositories. The research assesses the extent of overlap among these repositories, analyzes citation dynamics involving these research objects, and determines their integration within UNIBO's Current Research Information System ([IRIS](#)).

The Research Questions (RQs) are formulated as follows:

1. What is the current coverage of these kinds of research objects created by UNIBO personnel in existing repositories?
2. Is there any overlap among these repositories (i.e., research objects deposited in more than one)?

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3. How many citations (incoming and outgoing), as in OpenCitations, are these research objects involved in?
4. How much of such research objects are actually mapped in IRIS?

Methodology. The team systematically collected and analyzed metadata from selected institutional, disciplinary, and generalist repositories, including [AMS Acta](#), [Software Heritage](#), and [Zenodo](#). Data and metadata were extracted using APIs. Cross-repository depositions were identified to assess overlaps, and citation analysis tools, such as [OpenCitations](#), were employed to examine citation patterns. Additionally, the collected data were cross-referenced with IRIS to evaluate its coverage of these research outputs.

Findings. The analysis revealed that the coverage of the diverse research outputs produced by the personnel of the University of Bologna varies significantly across the selected repositories. AMS Acta primarily hosts institutional outputs, while Software Heritage focuses on software-related contributions, and Zenodo encompasses a broader range of interdisciplinary research objects. There is a notable overlap among these repositories with certain identical research objects being deposited across multiple repositories. Citation analysis indicates that while these research objects generate both incoming and outgoing citations, their citation networks are unevenly distributed, with software and databases receiving more frequent references. Moreover, a substantial portion of these research objects remains unmapped in IRIS, highlighting gaps in institutional tracking and integration. These findings emphasize the need for a more cohesive strategy to enhance visibility, discoverability, and interoperability across repositories.

Value. This study sheds light on the dissemination patterns and citation impact of UNIBO's diverse research outputs, providing insights to enhance their visibility and accessibility. The findings can inform strategies to optimize repository usage and improve the integration of these research objects within IRIS, ultimately strengthening open science practices at the University of Bologna and promoting a more cohesive approach for maximizing the impact of its research outputs.

Keywords. Scientometrics; Info-metrics; Metadata Mapping; Cross-Repository Analysis; Research Outputs; CRIS Systems; FAIR; Open Research Information.

1. Introduction

The growing interdisciplinary nature of modern research, coupled with the application of computational approaches to previously analog-only fields, has led to a significant increase in the creation of new and diverse research outputs, such as 3D models, virtual exhibitions, datasets, software, audiovisual materials, and grey literature (Okamura et al. 2019). However, tracking the dissemination of such outputs is becoming a challenge for universities and research institutions, which often lack a systematic approach to monitoring all materials produced and published by their researchers.

Universities commonly rely on Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) to track research outputs and manage associated metadata. CRIS platforms manage and exchange metadata related to research activities, typically including data about researchers, institutions, projects, and outputs. Over time, CRIS platforms have evolved to support the entire research lifecycle, serving both as public showcases of institutional research and as internal tools for strategic planning (De Castro and Puuska 2023). In Italy, most universities have adopted IRIS (<https://cris.unibo.it/>) (Bollini et al., 2016), a CRIS solution that enables researchers to directly contribute metadata about their scientific work².

Nevertheless, CRIS systems often fail to capture the full spectrum of the diverse research outputs, leading to gaps in institutional repositories and undermining the visibility of certain studies (Azeroual et al. 2018). In addition, populating a CRIS is a manual activity performed by researchers, who often focus on adding traditional publications only (e.g., journal articles, conference papers, books), thereby avoiding the addition of other research products to the system. This study examines these dynamics within the context of knowledge production at the University of Bologna (UNIBO), a prominent research institution that offers an interesting case study.

Specifically, we focus on how non-traditional research outputs, including datasets, software, and other kinds of research material, are disseminated by UNIBO-affiliated researchers. We analyse their contributions to various kinds of repositories, including an institutional repository (i.e. UNIBO AMSActa, <https://amsacta.unibo.it/>) (Vignocchi et al. 2006), a disciplinary repository (i.e. Software Heritage, <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>) (Di Cosmo and Zacchiroli, 2023)), and a general-purpose repository (i.e. Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/>) (European Organization For Nuclear Research and OpenAIRE, 2013)), and check how many of the considered research outputs discovered in these repositories are also described in IRIS, the UNIBO official CRIS system. Finally, we introduce another layer of analysis by studying the citation patterns of these publications through data provided by OpenCitations.

This study contributes to the field of Science of Science, which employs computational analysis of bibliographic and citation data to investigate knowledge creation, dissemination, and evolution (Fortunato et al. 2018). It also aligns with Open Science practices that promote transparency, collaboration, and accessibility throughout the research process (UNESCO, 2021). Understanding the patterns of dissemination beyond traditional journal articles and monographs is increasingly essential for universities seeking to promote the findability, accessibility, and reusability of diverse research outputs through open access publishing and data sharing practices.

To systematically investigate these dissemination patterns, this study addresses the following research questions:

² Learn more about the policies for depositing in the UNIBO's institutional repository [here](#).

1. What is the current coverage of diverse research outputs created by UNIBO in existing repositories?
2. Is there any overlap among these repositories (i.e., research objects deposited in more than one)?
3. How many citations (incoming and outgoing), as in OpenCitations, are these research objects involved in?
4. To what extent are these research outputs mapped and recorded in IRIS?

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we introduce the primary prior work on the topic of the research. In Section 3, we provide a comprehensive description of the materials and methodologies used to carry out the research with a particular focus on the tools and approaches that we have applied to guarantee the transparency and reproducibility of our study. In Section 4, the findings of the data analysis are presented, accompanied by infographics and useful visualisations, to provide a clear overview of the analysis outcomes. Lastly, in Section 5, the interpretation of the data and the impact of the research will be discussed to highlight key findings.

2. Related Work

Several institutions have increasingly focused on how research outputs are published and stored, particularly within the framework of Open Science. For example, Hurrell (2023) led a study at the University of Calgary examining the digital institutional repositories of 77 universities that are signatories of the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) (Cagan, 2013). The study found that even institutions committed to reforming research assessment struggle to prioritise the collection of non-traditional outputs such as datasets, software, and creative works in their institutional repositories. While 96% of repositories surveyed in the UK included some non-traditional content, these outputs represented only a small fraction of the total, with institutional focus remaining heavily skewed toward traditional publications. This suggests that, despite technical readiness and policy frameworks promoting inclusivity, a more active commitment is needed to elevate the visibility and integration of diverse scholarly outputs within institutional ecosystems.

In parallel with these policy-oriented studies, a significant body of work has also emerged around methodologies for cross-repository analysis, which is essential for understanding the broader landscape of research dissemination. Cross-repository matching typically involves specifying attributes – such as metadata fields like titles, authors, identifiers, or content descriptors – to identify duplicate records and overlapping content across repositories³. Recent advances include the use of binary classification models based on repository-level embeddings to predict conceptual similarity (Rokon et al., 2025), as well as multi-level analysis techniques that incorporate aspects such as source code, documentation, licensing, and dependency management (Zhang et al., 2024).

³ Further discussion on cross-repository matching and content overlap is available [here](#).

Other relevant works in this area include tools and frameworks like OpenAIRE's Research Graph, which integrates metadata from a variety of scholarly communication sources to build interconnected records (Manghi et al., 2019), and the Scholix Framework (Burton et al., 2017), a community-driven model for interoperable exchange and reuse of links between scholarly literature and datasets. Additionally, the OpenCitations initiative demonstrates how cross-repository linking and citation analysis can enrich metadata and improve discoverability across open infrastructures (Peroni and Shotton, 2020).

Together, these lines of research highlight both the policy-level challenges in repository adoption of non-traditional outputs and the technical innovations driving interoperability and large-scale repository analysis.

3. Materials and Methods

This section outlines the materials and methodologies used to carry out this research, with a particular focus on the tools and approaches applied to guarantee the transparency and reproducibility of our study.

3.1 Subjects and Research Design

The primary subjects of this study are non-traditional research outputs produced by personnel affiliated with the University of Bologna (UNIBO). Drawing on the taxonomy adopted in IRIS (Bollini et al. 2016) – the Institutional Research Information System used across Italian universities – these outputs include, but are not limited to: **software, databases, exhibitions, patents, multimedia content (such as audio and video), prototypes, datasets, and educational materials**. These forms of scholarly production extend beyond conventional publications – such as journal articles, books, book chapters, monographs, and conference proceedings – and represent a growing share of institutional knowledge assets within scholarly communication ecosystems.

To investigate how such outputs are stored, described, and disseminated, we employed a systematic methodology to collect and analyze associated metadata from a selection of repository types: institutional (AMS Acta), disciplinary (Software Heritage), and generalist (Zenodo). This multi-source design enables a comparative view of metadata practices across platforms and supports a broader reflection on the visibility and integration of diverse research contributions.

3.2 Data Sources

The study focused on metadata harvested from the following key repositories:

- **AMS Acta:** UNIBO's institutional open access repository, designed to ensure long-term open access to scientific outputs.

- **Software Heritage:** The world's largest public archive of software source code and associated development history, archiving over 16 billion unique source code files from more than 250 million projects (Di Cosmo and Zacchiroli, 2017).
- **Zenodo:** An interdisciplinary platform developed by CERN that provides secure long-term preservation and open metadata access.
- **IRIS (Current Research Information System):** UNIBO's CRIS platform used to evaluate the institutional integration and traceability of research objects.
- **OpenCitations:** Used for citation analysis to assess the impact and scholarly connectivity of the research outputs.

3.3 Data Collection

The procedure for data collection relied on API-based data extraction, ensuring structured and reliable access to metadata from all selected repositories. This approach enabled systematic harvesting of relevant data while preserving data integrity and consistency. Repositories such as Zenodo, Software Heritage, and OpenCitations were accessed through their dedicated API endpoints, while AMS Acta was accessed via its OAI-PMH API. This strategy aligns with the FAIR principles – making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable – and supports the broader push for interoperability in research data management (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

Specific details of the data collection process for each repository are provided in the following subsections. A comprehensive overview of the data collection workflow is also available in the official protocol of our research ([10.5281/zenodo.15742088](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15742088)). Additional information regarding data management practices can be found in our official Data Management Plan ([10.5281/zenodo.15742057](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15742057)).

3.3.1 Software Heritage Data Extraction

To identify software (SW) repositories affiliated with the University of Bologna within the SWH archive, we implemented data extraction pipeline⁴ with Python ([10.5281/zenodo.15740634](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15740634)), designed to programmatically search, retrieve, and filter relevant entries from software artefacts. This pipeline made extensive use of open-source libraries such as `requests` (for HTTP communication), `os` and `json` (for file and data handling), and `time` (to manage API throttling and delays). To ensure resilience against API rate limiting and transient connection issues, we employed `urllib3.util.retry` in conjunction with `requests.adapters.HTTPAdapter`, allowing the pipeline to automatically retry failed requests with exponential backoff. The use of `RetryError` and `Timeout` from `requests.exceptions` further supported robust error handling throughout the process.

The primary goal of the extraction was to isolate origins (i.e., source code repositories) likely associated with UNIBO by analysing two key signals: (1) the presence of institution-specific

⁴ All software developed for this research is available under license in our repository. See <https://github.com/open-sci/2024-2025/tree/main/crisis/code>.

keywords in README files and (2) email domains in commit metadata. The data extraction process employs the public API of Software Heritage (<https://archive.softwareheritage.org/api/1>).

The current identification approach adopts a simple heuristic-based method, prioritizing broad retrieval by relying on practical, approximate criteria to infer institutional affiliation. An initial keyword-based full-text search is performed using a predefined set of keywords (e.g., "unibo", "unibo.it", "university of bologna", "alma mater studiorum"). These keywords are passed to the full-text search API. Paginated results are resolved through Link headers to ensure comprehensive data retrieval. To optimise subsequent executions and reduce redundant API calls, the results of this initial keyword search are cached in a local JSON file (`cached_candidate_origins.json`).

For each discovered candidate software origin, a verification process is undertaken to confirm its institutional affiliation. This involves obtaining the latest visit snapshot, extracting the canonical branch (typically `main` or `master`), and fetching the associated revision and its directory structure. Two primary criteria are then applied to validate UNIBO affiliation:

- **README content inspection:** If a README file is present in the repository's root directory, its textual content is downloaded, converted to lowercase, and checked for the presence of the predefined university-specific keywords.
- **Author email domain filtering:** The complete commit log for the revision is parsed to identify authors or committers whose email addresses include the institutional domain (`@unibo.it`). The use of revision logs allows for a deep inspection of historical contributions, rather than relying solely on the latest commit metadata.

Given the extensive size of the SWH archive, our data collection process is designed to be fault-tolerant and to support long-running batch operations, including the ability to resume execution after interruptions. To achieve this, it maintains intermediate progress using two local JSON files. The file `processed_origins.json` records the index of the last successfully processed origin, thereby enabling resumable execution without redundant reprocessing. The file `unibo_repositories_swh.json` (shown in Listing 1) stores all validated repositories in a structured format, including the repository URL, revision identifier, directory identifier, and a deduplicated list of authors extracted from both revision metadata and commit logs. The final output comprises repositories satisfying one or both affiliation criteria, enabling downstream analysis of institutional software artefacts ([10.5281/zenodo.15741523](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15741523)).

The initial keyword-based extraction yielded approximately 4000 candidate entries, which were subsequently filtered down to around 1000 confirmed repositories through verification of institutional markers present in README files and contributor email addresses.

```
[
  {
    "url": "https://dei-gitlab.dei.unibo.it/mengozzi/thesis.git",
    "rev": "fab7f6bdad82bd420889943c42af0caaf9e1f30b",
```

```

"dir_id": "9f0aedc03bbcf0bb1f449684b52dd7b8aa3f8f92",
"authors": [
  {
    "name": "Mattia Mengozzi",
    "email": "mattia.mengozzi2@studio.unibo.it"
  }
],
{
"url": "https://github.com/CVLAB-Unibo/Learning2AdaptForStereo",
"rev": "549290859b6d5e81d2e3248a7066249508bfdd46",
"dir_id": "60cb80d0fb74814ea3f238ee419eff99451d989b",
"authors": [
  {
    "name": "Alessio Tonioni",
    "email": "alessio.tonioni@unibo.it"
  },
  {
    "name": "Alessio Tonioni",
    "email": "alex23settembre@gmail.com"
  },
  {
    "name": "GitHub",
    "email": "noreply@github.com"
  },
  {
    "name": "atonioni",
    "email": "alessio.tonioni@unibo.it"
  }
],
},
...
]

```

Listing 1: Excerpt from the output file *unibo_repositories_swh.json*, showing extracted UNIBO-affiliated repositories.

However, this approach has notable limitations – particularly the risk of missing relevant repositories due to naming inconsistencies and incomplete metadata – and could be significantly improved, as discussed in Section 5. In this study, it was not possible to cross-check the coverage between Software Heritage and IRIS due to the absence of shared persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) and the limited, non-standardized metadata exposed by the SWH API. The approach mentioned above, used to infer institutional affiliation in Software Heritage (e.g., commit email domains and README content), could not be reconciled with the

structured but publication-oriented metadata available in IRIS. As a result, direct linkage or overlap analysis between the two datasets was infeasible.

3.3.2 Zenodo Data Extraction

The data extraction from the general-purpose repository Zenodo was performed through the extremely well documented REST API (<https://developers.zenodo.org/#rest-api>) that the platform provides, specifically using the 'records' method . The process was implemented with a two-phase approach in order to comprehensively capture the research outputs associated with the University of Bologna. The first step involved querying record based on the "affiliation" strings, to ensure that all the possible denominations used for the university of Bologna were covered the search query contained: "University of Bologna", "Università di Bologna", "UNIBO", and "Alma Mater Studiorum" across both creators and contributors fields. To avoid the rate limits of the API the search employed pagination with 100 records per request and 1 second delays between requests. The second phase revolved around the use of the ORCID identifiers of researchers affiliated to the University of Bologna extracted from the institutional repository (IRIS) to catch any record that didn't contain information about the affiliation of the creators or contributors. The ORCID identifiers were processed in batches of 10 and used to create queries to search for research outputs that contained them while explicitly excluding records with a UNIBO affiliation to avoid duplication (10.5281/zenodo.15740634).

The extracted data follows the JSON Metadata Schema⁵ that allows for a rich description of each record. Additionally, to ensure reusability, each Zenodo record contains a minimum of mandatory terms from DataCite⁶ ([10.5281/zenodo.15741523](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15741523)).

The data extraction from Zenodo, with the REST API, produced 5434 records (3949 from the initial filtering by affiliation and 1485 from the queries created with the ORCID IDs extracted from IRIS). At this step it is important to analyze the different typologies of research product uploaded to the generalist repository by the researchers at UNIBO; precisely half of the records are labelled as "publication" while, interestingly, the second most uploaded typology is "dataset" with 1273 entries. Software appears to be a relatively rare research product counting only 352 records out of the 5434, the remaining results are divided into the following typologies: Physical object, workflow, video, lesson, event, model, image, presentation, poster and other.

3.3.3 AMS Acta Data Extraction

In the case of AMS Acta, metadata was retrieved via its OAI-PMH API endpoint (<https://amsacta.unibo.it/cgi/oai2>), using the Python library Sickie⁷. Sickie is a lightweight client designed to interact with OAI-PMH services. It facilitates harvesting of

⁵ Cf. [JSON Schema](#)

⁶ Cf. [DataCite Schema](#)

⁷ Cf. [Sickie 0.7.0](#)

metadata records by handling the OAI protocol natively and supporting automatic pagination via `resumptionToken`.

Our process began by querying the AMS Acta endpoint for metadata in the Dublin Core format (`oai_dc`)⁸. While this format provides a standardized structure for bibliographic data, it does not include detailed information about author affiliations, which was essential for our filtering goals. However, it did provide ePrint IDs, which served as stable identifiers for records in the AMS Acta repository.

At this stage, only the ePrint IDs were collected. For each harvested ePrint ID, a direct call was made to the JSON export URL, which returned structured metadata in JSON format (`amsacta_cleaned_metadata.json`). This enriched data was then stored locally for further analysis and filtering.

It is important to note that in some instances, affiliation data or ORCID identifiers were absent, even in the JSON records or the corresponding AMS Acta HTML pages. Nevertheless, the majority of records provided sufficient detail for filtering.

To isolate records associated to the University of Bologna, we implemented a two-pronged filtering strategy:

1. Affiliation-based filtering: Records were retained if at least one author's affiliation string contained the substrings *“bologna”* or *“unibo”*.
2. ORCID-based filtering: Records were also retained if at least one author's ORCID matched an entry from a CSV file provided by the University's IRIS system⁹, containing a verified list of institutional researchers.

In cases of multi-authored publications, the presence of at least one matching author – by affiliation or ORCID – was sufficient for inclusion in the final filtered dataset. This resulted in a final JSON file (`filtered_affiliation_or_orcid.json`), containing all the records in AMS Acta created by researchers affiliated with the University of Bologna.

The first extraction through the employment of the JSON exporter, after obtaining the ePrint IDs, reached around 5000 records, as it is the same number of publications present on AMS Acta, upon being filtered through the criteria explained in section 3.3.3, the number came to be around 1000 records belonging to researchers affiliated with the University of Bologna.

This also represents a distribution of the types of records contained inside of AMS Acta, with the diverse research outputs amounting to the combination of datasets and softwares to around 383 elements. In Figure 1, we show how the elements are distributed among different types.

⁸ Cf. [OAI-DC](#)

⁹ Cf. [UNIBO IRIS bibliographic data dump, dated 30 May 2025](#).

Figure 1: the number of records in AMS-Acta by type.

3.3.4 Data Merging

The merging process was carried out to consolidate all the data into a single file, making it easier to analyze and extract meaningful results and answer our research questions. The code for getting the following operations is available in the (`mashup.ipynb`) notebook in the software repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15740634>). Four datasets were used in this mashup:

- **Zenodo**
- **AMS Acta**
- **Software Heritage**
- **Iris**

The final dataset is built by **vertically concatenating** the records from the four source datasets. This means all datasets are **appended row-wise** into a single unified DataFrame, with column alignment based on shared field names. We have selected these rows based on the possibility of finding the types and related information in the fields like description, abstract, type, resource_type, keywords...

For all the datasets the creators and orcid numbers, in case they are available, are all appended to a list for each row.

Zenodo Dataset: The Zenodo dataset was in a JSON file (`ZenodoData.json`). It was first normalized by:

- Getting the metadata in the nested dictionaries and clean them
- Removing duplicate entries
- Cleaning the description field by stripping HTML tags using the *BeautifulSoup* library, converting it into plain text

The following keys were selected from Zenodo for the mashup:

- title: title of the record
- id: internal identifier assigned by Zenodo
- doi: the Digital Object Identifier
- creators: list of creators associated with the record
- orcid: list of ORCID IDs for the creators
- date: publication date
- description: metadata description
- resource_type: extracted from the "resource type" metadata field
- type: further specification of the record type
- rights: access rights (e.g., open, restricted)
- publisher: publishing entity (journal, book, university for theses; defaults to Zenodo if not specified)
- relation: PID of related records
- communities: community IDs mentioned in the metadata
- keywords: list of associated keywords
- Swh: id for software heritage

Additionally, we extracted the `swh_id` from the Zenodo records using regular expressions to enable cross-referencing with the Software Heritage dataset.

AMS Acta Dataset: The AMS Acta dataset, provided in a JSON format file (`filtered_affiliation_or_orcid.json`), was filtered to include the following keys for integration:

- doi
- creators: *given and family name* merged together
- monograph_type: types in case the type is monograph and inserted in resource_type
- type
- date
- uri
- publisher

- eprintid: used as the value for id column
- abstract: it is inserted in the description column
- issn
- keywords

In the original dataset, the names of the creators were nested with given and family names. We attached these two to be consistent with other datasets. Then we renamed the column names accordingly to be able to do the mashup.

Software Heritage Dataset: Software Heritage was the third dataset reviewed for this study. It was fetched via the API to the file (`unibo_repositories_swh.json`). Unfortunately, the API provided limited metadata and the dataset had minimal descriptive data. The accessible fields included: `urls`, `rev`, `dir_id`, `authors`.

From the URLs, we attempted to extract titles, but this method was imprecise and led to inconsistencies because the users have not chosen the exact and correct way of naming their repositories. Some of the repositories also were not accessible due to moving or deleting. The key field used for cross-dataset linking was `dir_id`, which we matched with the `sw_h_id` extracted from Zenodo to find overlaps.

Iris Dataset: The Iris dataset consisted of several massive files forming a comprehensive data dump (latest version: 30 May 2025). From each file, we extracted the following relevant columns: `id`, `creators`, `orcid`, `doi`, `url`, `pmid`, `date`, `title`, `type`, `publisher`, `issn`.

The IRIS dataset was large and split across multiple files. Some records appeared in only one of several files. We implemented logic to recover missing entries from other parts to preserve completeness, e.g., the first file, *“item with person”* and the second file *“item with description,”* presented inconsistencies: some records were missing from the primary files. To address this, we supplemented the dataset by retrieving missing entries from other files to ensure completeness. Then we joined different files in a single dataframe named ‘iris’ based on the id column. And remove duplicates and the rows with a missing id.

Then for every dataset a flag is added to determine the source dataset, adding it to the column label `src_repo`. In the final step we did a vertical concatenation of all data and produced a csv output file. The final csv file contains 419,829 records with a size of 120 MB. The final metadata labels are: `title`, `id`, `doi`, `creators`, `orcid`, `date`, `description`, `resource_type`, `url`, `type`, `rights`, `publisher`, `relation`, `communities`, `sw_h_id`, `keywords`, `src_repo`, `issn`, `pmid`.

3.4. Data Analysis

3.4.1. What is the current coverage of these research objects in existing repositories?

As for the methodology, the script `RQ1.py` ingests the whole mashup dataset in streaming mode (chunks = 100000 rows) so that the pipeline remains memory-light and reproducible on any machine.

A dictionary `iris_map` lists the 15 IRIS categories relevant to our project. For every incoming row the helper `classify_row()` concatenates the `type` and `resource_type` fields, lowers the case and tests the strings against the regular-expression list attached to each IRIS code. Rows that match any pattern receive a new label `iris_cat`, the others are discarded on the fly.

All labelled chunks are concatenated, producing `mashup_IRIS_subset_v3.csv` (8699 rows, 20 columns – the original metadata with the addition of `iris_cat`).

Repository	Objects in IRIS subset	Share of total
IRIS	4711	54%
Zenodo	2522	29%
Software Heritage	1014	12%
AMS Acta	452	5%
Total	8699	100%

Table 1: Population of IRIS subset.

3.4.2. Is there any overlap among these repositories – i.e. research objects deposited in more than one?

`RQ_2.py` works on the IRIS-filtered table. Two main strategies were used to detect duplicates among the repositories:

1. **DOI match:** As the DOI is the most authoritative, cross-platform identifier for scholarly objects, it was chosen as the basis for the main strategy for finding duplicates. If two rows expose exactly the same DOI (case-insensitive), we can be sure they describe the same object.
2. **Title match:** Many IRIS and AMS Acta records lack a DOI, and Zenodo versions may carry a different DOI (pre-print vs. published record). An exact, punctuation-free, lower-case title match catches these while still avoiding fuzzy “near-misses”.

We also checked the two identifier columns (`swh_id`, `pmid`) but no value occurred in more than one repository, so they contributed zero extra matches.

3.4.3. How many citations (incoming and outgoing), as in OpenCitations, are these research objects involved in?

To address the third research question, we developed a Python-based pipeline to extract and evaluate citation relationships using the [OpenCitations API](#). The following Python libraries have been used: `pandas`, `requests`, `tqdm`, and `logging`. The machine used for the computing has the following features:

Processore 12th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-12900H 2.90 GHz,
RAM installata 32,0 GB (31,7 GB utilizzabile),
Tipo sistema Sistema operativo a 64 bit, processore basato su x64

That resulted in an execution time of 1:10:24.

The API can be queried both using a valid DOI and using a PMID. Starting from the filtered `mashup_IRIS_subset.csv` only the entries with non-null DOIs were retained (`df["doi"].dropna()`), ensuring valid identifiers for citation lookup. Since from the subset relevant to our research none of the entries had a PMID value, that column wasn't utilised for our research project.

Each DOI was queried against two OpenCitations endpoints:

- `/references/{doi}` – to retrieve outgoing citations (works cited by the object)
- `/citations/{doi}` – to retrieve incoming citations (works citing the object)

This allowed for a bidirectional mapping of citation flow. Data was fetched iteratively, with the script handling API rate limits and retry logic to ensure stability. A log file has been created to keep track of the status of each call and of any potential error, with correlative DOI; the rate limits have been handled as follows:

time_parameter	value
timeout	15s - maximum time allowed for each <code>session.get()</code> request
pause	7s - pause between retries in case of a general error
pause * 2	14s - extended pause used only when status code <code>429</code> (rate limit) occurs
max_retries	3 times - maximum number of retry attempts per API call

Table 2: Time parameters to handle API calling.

We collected:

- the number of incoming (`cit_num_ingoing`) and outgoing (`cit_num_outgoing`) citations
- the Open Citation Identifiers (`oci`) for each direction
- a status field flagging failed or successful API retrievals

An example of the extracted structure per entry:

```

{
  "doi": "10.5281/zenodo.5504259",
  "cit_num_outgoing": 3,
  "cit_num_ingoiing": 5,
  "oci_outgoing": ["oci:1", "oci:2", "oci:3"],
  "oci_ingoiing": ["oci:4", "oci:5", "oci:6", "oci:7", "oci:8"],
  "status": "ok"
}

```

The retrieved results are then stored in lists of dictionaries, with a check on the ‘oci’ to avoid duplicates, and the final Dataframe is exported in as `CitationsCount.csv`.

Due to performance inconsistencies when using token-based authentication, we chose to access the OpenCitations API with a mock token, which proved more reliable for batch querying.

3.4.4 How much of such research objects are actually mapped in IRIS?

To further quantify the degree of overlap (as partially shown in Table 3, Results – RQ2), we aimed to calculate the percentage of Zenodo and AMS Acta objects already present in IRIS. To do so, we used the `duplicate_objects_v3.csv` file and constructed three separate dataframes—one for each repository: IRIS, Zenodo, and AMS Acta. Since Software Heritage was previously confirmed to have no overlapping entries, it was excluded from this step.

The analysis first attempted matching by DOI, where available. For records without DOIs or where DOI formatting differed, we implemented a secondary check using the “title” field. This two-step matching process allowed us to estimate total overlap coverage between repositories. The final count identified 82 overlapping entries between IRIS and Zenodo, and 51 between IRIS and AMS Acta.

4. Results

The following section presents the results ([10.5281/zenodo.15740634](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15740634)) obtained from the analysis of the collected data, structured according to the four research questions. Each subsection highlights key findings related to repository coverage, cross-repository overlap, citation patterns, and IRIS mapping.

4.1 What is the current coverage of these kinds of research objects created by UNIBO personnel in existing repositories?

The purpose of the first research question was to determine the coverage of each repository - Zenodo, Amsacta and Software Heritage - for the research objects relevant to our project. To address this problem we included the IRIS dump into our merged dataset and we approached it with an heuristic algorithm to create equivalencies between the different taxonomies in order to extract the relevant data (Table 1).

Figure 2: Population of IRIS subset.

Category highlights (all repositories combined, Fig. 2):

- 7.12 Mostra/Esposizione – 1996 objects (all from IRIS; mirrors UNIBO’s strong museum/exhibition activity).
- 7.04 Software – 1986 objects (Software Heritage ≈1000; IRIS = 589; Zenodo = 375; AMS Acta = 8).
- 7.05 Banche dati – 1907 objects, largely hosted in Zenodo.
- 7.13 Rapporto tecnico – 1356 objects (IRIS 838; Zenodo 449; AMS Acta 69).

	iris_cat	count
0	7.12 Mostra o Esposizione	1996
1	7.04 Software	1986
2	7.05 Banche dati	1907
3	7.13 Rapporto tecnico	1356
4	7.07 Disegno	387
5	7.03 Prodotto dell'ingegneria civile e dell'ar...	252
6	7.09 Performance	189
7	7.06 Composizione musicale	169
8	7.10 Manufatto	156
9	7.01 Carta tematica e geografica	120
10	7.15 Test psicologici	87
11	7.02 Carta geologica	75
12	7.08 Design	10
13	7.11 Prototipo d'arte e relativi progetti	9

Figure 3: Population of subsets according to IRIS categories.

The matrix confirms that IRIS is the single largest host, especially for artistic/performance artefacts, while Zenodo extends the institutional record with datasets and software. Software Heritage contributes only the software category, as expected, but at a scale comparable to Zenodo. AMS Acta's share is modest and almost entirely overlaps IRIS categories¹⁰.

4.2 Is there any overlap among these repositories (i.e., research objects deposited in more than one)?

Rows whose DOI or title occurs in ≥ 2 repositories are copied into `duplicate_objects_v3.csv` and annotated with `dup_reason = {doi, title, doi-title}`. In order to condense all those individual duplicate rows into an at-a-glance scoreboard, a helper `repo_pairs()` converts the per-identifier repo lists into counts for each repo-pair.

As a result of applying the described strategies, the following outcomes were found:

- 285 rows (3.3 % of the 8699 row subset) appear in more than one repository.
- Overlaps are confined to the three institutional/generalist repositories; no Software Heritage object duplicates anything outside its archive.

¹⁰ For more detailed information, please see `mashup_IRIS_subset_v3.csv`.

Repository pair	Objects shared	Main duplicate types
AMS Acta — IRIS	45	7.13 Rapporto tecnico 7.05 Banche dati
IRIS — Zenodo	40	7.13 Rapporto tecnico 7.05 Banche dati 7.04 Software
AMS Acta — Zenodo	4	7.13 Rapporto tecnico

Table 3: The number of objects shared between each repository

One research object can sit in two repositories (yielding 2 rows) or even three (yielding 3 rows), so the total row count (285) is larger than the sum of the object-pair counts. dup_reason distribution shows that 157 rows collide on both DOI and title, 25 on DOI-only, and 103 on title-only. Category analysis of the 285 duplicates reveals that 7.05 *Banche dati* (119 rows) and 7.13 *Rapporto tecnico* (108 rows) account for 80 % of the overlaps, with smaller pockets in 7.04 *Software* (36 rows).

Figure 4: Cross-repository duplicates

4.3 How many citations (incoming and outgoing), as in OpenCitations, are these research objects involved in?

The purpose of the third research question is to have a quantitative result on the number of ingoing and outgoing citations for the selected objects to detect the usage and involvement among researchers. After collecting all the citations from the API we need to reassign each DOI to its original repository:

```
df_mashup = pd.read_csv("C:/Users/annan/Downloads/mashup_v3.csv")
doi_to_repo = dict(zip(df_mashup['doi'], df_mashup['src_repo']))
```

Then, with the method `.iterrows()` we calculate the total of ingoing and outgoing citations for each repository and store it in two dictionaries.

```
Total ingoing citations count: {'amsacta': 16, 'software heritage': 0,
'zenodo': 378, 'iris': 1204}
```

```
Total outgoing citations count: {'amsacta': 0, 'software heritage': 0,
'zenodo': 392, 'iris': 2070}
```


Figure 5: The Ingoing and Outgoing Citations per Repository

As shown in the diagram (Fig. 5), the number of citations is generally proportional to the number of records per repository. However, despite Zenodo having approximately half the number of

records compared to IRIS, it accounts for only about one third of the total citations. In Zenodo, the number of ingoing and outgoing citations is nearly balanced, whereas IRIS shows a predominance of outgoing citations. It is important to note that entries from Software Heritage are zero in this analysis, as they do not include DOIs and thus could not be matched to citation data.

From the citations_error.log we can see that only three calls weren't successful:

10.5281/zenodo.3956457

10.5281/zenodo.7669736

10.5281/zenodo.7041697

The reported error is: HTTPSConnectionPool(host='opencitations.net', port=443).

4.4 How much of such research objects are actually mapped in IRIS?

Given the nature of our initial mashup of repositories - adding not only AMS Acta, Zenodo and Software Heritage but also IRIS dump - the overlap analysis carried out for RQ2 also provides a direct answer to the fourth research question (see Table 3). By comparing IRIS with the other repositories, we identified 45 unique objects that appear in both AMS Acta and IRIS, and 40 unique objects shared between Zenodo and IRIS.

When these figures are compared to the total number of records retrieved from each repository (Table 1), we observe that only **3.25%** of Zenodo entries (82 out of 2522) are also found in IRIS, and **11.3%** of AMS Acta entries (51 out of 452) are duplicated in IRIS. These results confirm that while a portion of research outputs from external repositories are already mapped in the university's CRIS, the overall overlap remains limited.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

This study highlights the fragmented yet promising landscape of heterogeneous research output dissemination at the University of Bologna. Our findings demonstrate that while IRIS remains the dominant institutional repository for these research objects (54% of entries), generalist platforms like Zenodo (29%) and disciplinary archives like Software Heritage (12%) significantly extend the coverage, particularly for datasets and software. AMS Acta, though more modest in scale, still contributes to the preservation of institutional knowledge, especially technical reports and data-related records.

The overlap analysis reveals that only 3.3% of research objects are duplicated across multiple repositories, indicating that many non-traditional outputs remain siloed. This may reflect either platform specialization or a broader lack of coordinated deposition strategies. Notably, Software Heritage appears entirely non-overlapping with other repositories, underscoring both its specificity and the challenges of interoperability.

Citation data from OpenCitations further confirms disparities in visibility and scholarly engagement. IRIS records dominate citation activity (with over 1200 incoming and 2000 outgoing citations), followed by Zenodo. In contrast, Software Heritage entries, despite their volume and potential value, recorded no citation activity, due to limited metadata connectivity and the marginal role software still plays in formal citation practices.

These findings carry important implications for institutional research evaluation and Open Science policy. First, the relatively low representation of non-traditional outputs in IRIS – despite their presence elsewhere – suggests a systemic gap in the university’s internal tracking. This compromises discoverability, limits the recognition of diverse scholarly contributions, and potentially distorts research assessment frameworks. Second, the results highlight the importance of repository interoperability. The absence of cross-repository linking mechanisms hampers integration, discoverability, and citation flow.

From a methodological perspective, the current Software Heritage extraction pipeline, although effective, is time-consuming, with a runtime of approximately ~40 hours. This extended duration reflects not only the complexity of the heuristic filtering process but also the immense scale of the Software Heritage archive, which contains over 22 billion source files from 341 million projects and occupies more than 800 TB of compressed storage¹¹. Given these dimensions, optimizing the pipeline is both necessary and promising.

Future improvements could involve refining the filtering criteria by expanding the keyword set to include department acronyms (e.g., *Dipartimento*, *DISI*, *FICLIT*, etc.) and campus names (e.g., *Campus di Cesena*, *Campus di Ravenna*, *Campus di Rimini*). In addition, a confidence-based scoring system could replace the current binary checks. This system would assign weights to multiple affiliation signals – such as matches in repository URLs, author email domains, and README content – and evaluate repositories based on a cumulative score, with the goal of improving recall without compromising precision. Furthermore, automating integration with IRIS could streamline researcher workflows and contribute to more comprehensive and consistent metadata coverage across institutional systems.

In broader terms, this work underscores the need for coordinated efforts to align institutional repositories with Open Science infrastructures. Achieving true interoperability depends not only on technical harmonization – e.g., metadata schemas – but also on procedural and cultural shifts in how researchers publish and register their outputs. Repositories should aim to support interoperability “by design”, enabling cross-platform citation, discovery, and usage analytics.

In conclusion, the University of Bologna – like many institutions globally – is at a pivotal juncture in its Open Science journey. By embracing practices that prioritize inclusivity of research outputs, improve cross-repository alignment, and foster better integration into IRIS, the university can lead in promoting transparency, accessibility, and impact across the full spectrum of scholarly communication.

¹¹ For additional information on Software Heritage archive and its internal storage architecture, please refer to the official [documentation](#).

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